

Data Management Plan – HOT-HPC project

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Project Title	Architectures, Frameworks and Applications of High Performance Computing
Project Acronym	HOT-HPC
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Starting date	September 1st, 2023
Duration	36 months

1 Summary

The HOT-HPC project (*arcHitectures, framewOrks and applicaTions of High Performance Computing*) aims to advance the state of the art in HPC by addressing challenges across three major research lines. In the architectural domain, the project focuses on optimizing reconfigurable hardware (FPGAs), developing data-specific compilation techniques for emerging architectures, and benchmarking quantum computing platforms (NISQ) in conjunction with classical HPC systems. These efforts are designed to improve performance, energy efficiency, and adaptability in heterogeneous computing environments.

In terms of frameworks and applications, HOT-HPC will develop efficient algorithms for CPU-GPU systems, elastic Big Data platforms in serverless environments, and HPC-accelerated solutions for computational biology, genomics, and machine learning. The project emphasizes real-world impact through collaborations with industry and research centers, targeting domains such as bioinformatics, autonomous systems, and quantum computing. By integrating cutting-edge technologies and fostering interdisciplinary innovation, HOT-HPC seeks to position Galicia and Spain at the forefront of European HPC research and development.

This *Data Management Plan* (DMP) lays down the guidelines for the management of the data generated and used by the HOT-HPC project. This DMP includes information describing the data, objectives and procedure, security and long-term preservation measures, license of use and responsible persons. It follows the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

This is document version 1.1, the intermediate DMP, and will be updated during the project’s life cycle if and when relevant changes occur and, as well as for the final report.

2 Data summary

During the development of the project, we will gather, use and generate the following data types:

- **Experimental inputs:** these include input datasets for HPC simulations and applications. Examples include sparse matrices belonging to different domains (e.g., circuit simulation, geographical data, chemistry, etc.) or pre-trained ML models. These inputs will be collected mostly from public sources, e.g., the SuiteSparse repository for sparse matrices, the Hugging Face transformers library, or the (now deprecated) Sparse Zoo neural network model repository. These are typically available using standard formats (e.g., MTX, RB, or MATLAB-like for matrices; the *safetensors*, ONNX or PyTorch formats for neural network models). These will be collected from open-source repositories, and are distributed under a broad collection of such as Apache license 2.0, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0, Creative ML OpenRAIL-M, or the Llama2 Community License.
- **Software and source code:** developed in the context of the project, will be distributed after publication under open-source licenses. It will be made available in public repositories, such as GitHub, and particularly under the UDC-GAC organization.
- **Analysis and simulation results:** these include the output from linear algebra computations, genomic analyses, CSB simulations, etc. These are typically generated in custom binary formats which are completely dependent on the simulation at hand. In our project, these results are known beforehand and are part of the input to the problem. We develop and benchmark optimized execution strategies, and use the results only for validation. As such, these results are discarded after an experiment finishes.
- **Experimental benchmarking data:** these include data related to the execution time and energy efficiency of the simulations, and are generated by research lines with a focus on performance optimization. They are captured using tabular formats, e.g., CSV files. Benchmarking data will be made public as part of artifact packages, as detailed below.
- **Scientific papers and public engagement materials:** following the mandate of the related funding bodies (MCIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and “ERDF A way of making Europe”, EU), these will be made available under open-access license, and/or through open repositories such as the GAC space in the institutional RUC repository from the Universidade da Coruña. Whenever possible, published scientific papers will undergo an artifact evaluation process, a formal mechanism used by conferences and journals in the computer science and engineering fields to assess the quality and reproducibility of digital resources. The resulting research artifact will be made available through Zenodo, a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN, where the GAC has its own Zenodo-GAC community.

3 Documentation and Metadata

We aim to follow standard metadata format from recognized reference repository platforms used for data sharing as described above (e.g. GitHub, Zenodo, etc.). Examples of metadata types include authors, contributors, titles, publication date, descriptions, keywords, funding information, and licenses and rights. Software and source codes distributed through GitHub or other public repositories will be accompanied by “LICENSE“ and “README“ files, containing licensing and operational information. Additionally, research artifacts will be accompanied by the corresponding PDF appendix describing all software, hardware and data set dependencies, key results to be reproduced, and how to prepare, run, and validate experiments.

4 Ethical and Privacy Considerations, and Intellectual Property Rights

No personal data will be managed in this project, nor is the direct participation of human or animal subjects planned. All European and Spanish regulations, including GDPR, and LOPD-GDD, will be observed. Intellectual property will be managed according to UDC regulations and susceptible research results will be protected through appropriate licensing and, whenever appropriate, software registers and patents.

Ownership of intellectual property rights will be retained by the actor(s) that generated the work. In particular, the property rights of software products and research papers and artifacts will be retained by Universidade da Coruña and their employees involved in the development of the associated subtask in the project.

5 Safety, Storage, Preservation, and Sharing

We aim to use managed storage provided by the hosting institution (UDC-CITIC) to store intermediate products and research developments, taking advantage of their built-in secured access and redundancy services.

Valuable final products, such as research artifacts, software and scientific papers will be published in public, open repositories as described above, such as GitHub, RUC-GAC, and Zenodo-GAC. We will rely on the reliability characteristics of these platforms, while keeping local copies of the final products in the hosting institution media for failsafe purposes. Persistent identifiers (DOI) will be assigned to each product when possible.

Using these strategies and infrastructures, we will follow the National Strategy for Open Science 2023 – 2027 (ENCA) of the AEI, ensuring open access to research results with FAIR treatment: software products, resulting data, and scientific papers will be made **F**indable through open channels such as GitHub, and Zenodo, and **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, and **R**eusable under open licenses and by accompanying them of appropriate descriptions and relevant metadata.

6 Responsible Persons

The responsibility for establishing and supervising the implementation of the Data Management Plan (DMP) falls on the Principal Investigators of the project. In addition, all research team members are co-responsible of generating, annotating, and distributing the data through the channels in this data management plan and following the established protocols. These activities are transversal to the scientific developments in the project. It is the responsibility of each research line coordinator to initiate these tasks for each susceptible research result (benchmarking data, software, research paper, etc.), and escalate the actions taken.